

Grant agreement no.:
101060634

Project acronym:
PURPEST

Project full title:
Plant pest prevention through technology-guided monitoring and site-specific control

Collaborative Project (RIA Research and Innovation action)

HORIZON EUROPE CALL – HORIZON-CL6-2021-FARM2FORK-01

Start date of project: 2023-01-01
Duration: 4 years

D 1.2

List of VOCs and VOC patterns of pests from pure culture

Due delivery date: 31-03-2024
Actual delivery date: 02-04-2024

Organization name of lead contractor for this deliverable:
NIBIO

Project co-funded by the European Commission within HORIZON 2020 (2016-2020)		
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	x
CO	Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement	
CI	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.	

Deliverable number:	D 1.2
Deliverable name:	List of volatile organic compounds from pests in pure culture

Work package:	WP1
Lead contractor:	NIBIO

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Abstract
<p>Volatile organic compounds are produced by all living organisms. Identifying species-specific VOC profiles is the first step towards exploiting these compounds for pest detection and monitoring in a plant health and phytosanitary context. In this study, we collected VOCs from <i>Phytophthora ramorum</i> and 30 related oomycete species, the Pinewood nematode (<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>), the Brown marmorated stink bug (<i>Halyomorpha halys</i>), the Southern green stink bug (<i>Nezara viridula</i>) and the Fall armyworm (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>). The VOCs were captured on thermal desorption tubes or adsorbent filters, using a custom-made head space collection device. The compounds were identified by comparing the mass spectra of the captured VOCs with commercial standards in the NIST Mass spectra library. All tested organisms consistently produced unique VOC profiles, except for one oomycete, which did not produce any detectable VOC consistently enough for consideration. These promising results support our hypothesis that VOCs can be exploited for plant pest identification and detection. In our following studies we will investigate if these pest related VOCs will also be detected around host plants attacked by them.</p>

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1 INTRODUCTION

Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are produced by living organisms either constitutively or in response to physio-chemical changes in their environment. The VOCs that are produced can be general or highly specific, often they are very dynamic. These features make VOCs the ideal biomarkers to detect plant pests, as VOC profiles could be produced exclusively, but reliably, by some pest species and not by others. Identifying and monitoring VOC profiles also allows us to exploit them to follow changes in the plant health status, as plants respond to biotic and abiotic stresses with changes in their VOC profiles as well. In order to detect target pests in or on their host plant, it is important to know the VOC profile of the pest by itself first and so determine if the VOC profile from plants infested with the pest contains the identified pest-specific VOCs. This might not always be the case as the pest-specific VOC profiles can change with their metabolism adapting from being in pure culture to attacking and invading a host. The concentration of VOCs produced by pests is also expected to be significantly lower than from the host plant and therefore a lot more difficult to detect. However, detection of a pest-specific VOC in both pure culture and on the hostplant invaded by the pest, makes this particular VOC a highly promising candidate for a robust and specific marker for this target pest.

With the experiments in the first phase of the PurPest project, we hope to establish that VOCs can be species-specific for a very diverse and broad group of pests, including oomycete pathogens, nematodes and insects.

The materials and methods below describe our work on determining pest specific VOC profiles from four target pests without their hosts in pure culture. The target pests or groups of pests we have selected include the group of *Phytophthora* species comprising soil- or airborne plant pathogens, such as *P. ramorum* and *P. cinnamomi* with an extremely large host range; the Pinewood nematode (PWN, *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus*) a quarantine pest causing pine wilt disease, the Brown marmorated stink bug (BMSB, *Halyomorpha halys*), attacking important fruit and horticultural crops, and the Fall armyworm (FAW, *Spodoptera frugiperda*), a quarantine pest attacking maize and over 60 other important food crops. The lists of VOCs produced by these pests in pure culture are listed under the result section.

Research on VOCs related to the Cotton bollworm (CBW, *Helicoverpa armigera*) started in the 1970s with the identification of sex pheromones (Piccardi et al. 1977; Nesbitt et al. 1980; Zhang et al. 2012). Therefore, the CBW will not be tested without its host in this study. Oviposition deterring pheromones (ODPs) were first identified for CBW around the turn of the millennium (Guoqing et al. 2001; Xu et al. 2006; Liu et al. 2008) and a complete list of the oviposition deterrents found from CBW in our studies will be included in Deliverable 1.4 (List of VOCs from oviposition deterrents) at the end of 2024.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 *Phytophthora ramorum* and related species:

The VOCs of 32 oomycete species, including two isolates of *P. ramorum* lineages IC1 and NP2 from Asia were collected in pure culture (Table 1) using a custom-made fragrance collector (Flusys Type FSP-2246F 2023). One agar plug per actively growing oomycete colony was transferred to clarified V8 juice (cV8) agar in plastic Petri dishes. The plates were incubated in the dark at 20°C for the number of days required to get a colony radius of 3.5 to 4 cm (Table 1). Plastic Petri dishes with cV8 agar, but without any oomycete isolate served as the control. For the collection of VOCs, two agar plates per isolate were placed in an inert oven bag (polyethylene terephthalate 35 x 45 mm) that was attached to an inlet and an outlet. Charcoal filtered air was moved through the inlet, across the agar or culture and exited through the outlet, before it was captured on a Tenax TA35/60 (Markes) desorption filter. The air stream was regulated to ensure that 108 L were moved across the agar plates at a steady rate of 0,6 L/min. for 3 hours. At each collection time, 6 collections were made, one from the control (cV8 without isolate) and five from cV8 plates inoculated with one of the listed isolates. The collection of each isolate was repeated 5 times.

After the collection was finished, the Tenax tubes were desorbed on a Matrix TD GC-MS. The resulting peaks were analyzed and compared with the NIST Mass spectra library to compare the obtained spectra with the reference list and identify the compounds. Analysis was performed by separating compounds associated with the control from the compounds associated with the cultures. Further analyses were performed by cross experiment comparison to eliminate compounds produced by the control. After removing those compounds associated with the control, the remaining compounds were listed and will be considered for their biological role and potential to function as a species-specific signal (Figure 1).

Table 1 List of isolates for VOC collection.

Number	Species	Code	Number of growth days before VOC collection	ExpID*
1	<i>P. quercetorum</i>	QUT	10	5
2	<i>P. foliorum</i>	FOL	13	6
3	<i>P. ramorum</i> NP2	RP2	10	7
4	<i>P. ramorum</i> IC1	RI1	10	8
5	<i>Phytophthium litorale</i>	PL	5	9
6	<i>P. nagai</i>	NAG	6	10
7	<i>P. furcata</i>	FUR	5	11
8	<i>P. tropicalis</i>	TRO	6	12
9	<i>P. nicotianae</i>	NIC	10	13
10	<i>Phytophthium citrinum</i>	PC	5	14
11	<i>P. multivora</i>	MUL	10	15
12	<i>P. pseudosyringae</i>	PSE	11	16
13	<i>P. palmivora</i>	PAL	11	17
14	<i>P. castaneae</i>	CAS	11	18
15	<i>P. elongata</i>	ELO	11	19
16	<i>Phytophthium vexans b</i>	PVb	5	20
17	<i>Phytophthium vexans a</i>	PVa	5	21

18	<i>P. occultans</i>	OCC	10	22
19	<i>P. parvispora</i>	PAR	10	23
20	<i>P. plurivora</i>	PLU	5	24
21	<i>P. cinnamomi</i>	CIN	5	25
22	<i>P. inundata</i>	INU	9	26
23	<i>P. crassamura</i>	CRA	9	27
24	<i>P. xcambivora</i>	CAM	7	28
25	<i>P. cactorum</i>	CAC	7	29
26	<i>P. infestans</i>	INF	20	30
27	<i>P. lilii</i>	LIL	20	31
28	<i>P. hibernalis</i>	HIB	20	32
29	<i>Nothophytophthora intricata</i>	NI	20	33
30	<i>Pythium myriotylum</i>	PM	5	34
31	<i>P. pseudocryptogea</i>	PSC	7	35
32	<i>P. citrophthora</i>	CIP	8	36

*ExpID = experiment identification number

2.2 Pinewood nematode (PWN)

Steam sterilised barley seeds in 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks were inoculated with the fungus *Botrytis cinerea* under sterile conditions, flasks were covered with aluminium foil and plastic. The fungus grew in darkness, at 25 °C for 10 days, before 1 mL of a mixed life stage PWN suspension in sterile water (on average 2000 nematodes) was added. After 3, 6 and 7 days at the same conditions, VOCs from the PWN culture were sampled using the fragrance collector (Flusys Type FSP-2246F-2023) in the closed loop mode. For each infected nematode culture, a control fungal culture without the nematode was sampled in parallel. A charcoal filtered airstream was pushed across the sample cultures at 0.6 L/min for approximately 2h 45min to a total volume of 100 L.

After finishing the collection of VOCs on Tenax TA (Markes) tubes, these tubes were immediately sent to the University of Évora for analysis. TD-GC-MS chromatograms were analysed with AMDIS software and using the NIST library as described above. By comparing samples from fungal cultures (control) and samples from nematodes feeding on these cultures, we selected those compounds that were consistently present in samples from monoxenic PWN cultures.

2.3 Brown marmorated Stinkbug (BMSB)

To investigate VOCs of BMSB, volatiles released by egg masses (n = 5; approx. 50 eggs per replicate), first and second instar nymphs and their exuvia (n = 3-5; 10 nymphs/exuvia per replicate), and adult (n = 5; 3 males plus 2 females per replicate) were sampled. Before sampling adult BMSB, VOCs from males and females were sampled separately. Comparison of the VOCs chromatograms from male and female BMSB showed very similar chromatograms and released VOCs. Therefore, the mixed male and female adults were used for VOC collection. In order to determine if the VOC profile was indeed species-specific, the Southern green stink bug (SGSB), *Nezara viridula*, closely related to the BMSB was also included in the study.

Chemical patterns among different life stages of BSMB were investigated by using the fragrance collector (Flusys Type FSP-2246F-2023) in closed loop sampling mode. To collect volatiles, the eggs, nymphs, exuvia, and adults of BSMB were placed in glass bottles. Using clean air filter cartridges (ICAF 2X6, Sigma Scientific, Micanopy, USA), the stream of ambient air was purified and pumped, controlled by the Flusys fragrance collector, through each bottle at a rate of 0,6 L/min until it reached the final volume of 30 L. Volatile organic compounds from headspace sampling were trapped on stainless steel, prepacked sample tubes with Tenax TA35/60 sorbent (Markes, Neu-Isenburg, Germany). Moreover, there were control glass bottles in each round of VOC collection to avoid identifying unexpected VOCs from plastic, and glass bottles in BMSB samples. Afterwards, the chemical analysis of the sampled VOCs was performed using an automated thermal desorption system (TurboMatrix™ ATD 650, PerkinElmer, Rodgau, Germany) connected to a gas chromatograph coupled with a mass spectrometer (TD-GC-MS). The mass spectra of the collected compounds were identified by comparing them with the commercial standards in the NIST spectra library.

Raising the insects, collecting and analyzing the collected VOCs were conducted both at the JKI and at UNIPD.

2.4 Fall Army Worm

Caterpillars of the fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda* were fed on either a wheat germ-based artificial diet, maize leaves or bean plants 24 hours before the VOC collections. Then, they were placed in one-port glass bottles for head space collection of VOCs.

Clean moist air entered each bottle at 0.7 L/min flow rate and exited through a 25 mg of Hayesep-Q 80/100 mesh adsorbent filter (Ohio Valley Specialist Company, Marietta, USA) at 0.4 L/min. The volatiles were collected for two hours (48 L of total airflow through the filter per sample) and the filters were eluted with 80µL of dichloromethane (Honeywell, Riedel-de Haën, DE), and 5 µL of internal standard was added (n-nonyl acetate, 20 ng/µL each). The samples were stored at -80°C until further analyses. We used larvae from different age groups: young larvae (group of 30 larvae of 3rd instar), old larvae (group of 12 or 5 larvae of 5th to 6th instar) and 2 to 3 days-old pupae (group of 8-to 10 pupae). Larvae from the old group (5th and 6th instar) were then fed on the same diet until pupation to use them for the second round of VOC collection. To better separate the odors from the larvae itself and their excrements, we sampled the frass from old larvae. For that, we individualized each larva without any food supply for 3 hours and then the frass was collected. One sample was the combination of frass from 5 to 8 larvae. All samples were weighted before and the larvae were counted before and after the volatile collection, as the species is cannibalistic. We captured VOCs from three to five replications of larvae fed on 3 different diets.

The volatile samples were analyzed using a gas chromatograph (Agilent 7890B) coupled to a mass spectrometer (Agilent 5977B) in TIC mode. The identification and quantification of volatile compounds were performed based on comparing the mass spectra of commercial standards and the NIST Mass spectra library. Kovats index was calculated by injecting alkanes C8 to C40 (Sigma) and used for identification as well.

The FAW specific VOCs listed in the table below (Table 5) were chosen based on the amount produced and their consistent presence in headspace from larvae samples.

3 RESULTS

3.1 *Phytophthora ramorum* and related species

Each of the *Phytophthora* isolates and related species produced a different mixture of VOCs, except for *P. lili*, which did not produce any detectable VOCs (Table 2). The number of VOCs produced by each isolate varied between 0 (*P. lili*) and 13 (*Pythium myriotylum*). VOC profiles from the same species, but from different isolates, were similar but not identical. The VOC profile from *P. ramorum* NP2 (RP2) and *P. ramorum* IC1 (RI1) differed by only one VOC, namely 3-Hexen-2-one. VOC profiles from the two isolates from *Phytophthora vexans* differed in the number and type of VOCs. While one *Phytophthora vexans* isolate produced one VOC (2-methyl-1-Propanol) in addition to the 5 common *P. vexans* VOCs, the other isolate produced 3 additional VOCs (2,6-dimethyl-5-Hepten-1-ol, Citronellol and 2-methoxy-Phenol) from the 5 VOCs the two isolates had in common.

Table 2 Volatile organic compounds detected from 32 *Phytophthora* cultures. The compounds associated with cultures were sorted according to the reproducibility of the results. Orange indicated that the compounds were detected in four or five out of the five replicates.

Compound	FOL	QUIT	RP2	RI1	PL	NAG	FUR	TRO	NIC	PC	MUL	PSE	PAL	CAS	ELO	Pva	PVb	CIN	OCC	PAR	PLU	CAM	CAC	CRA	INU	HIB	INF	LIL	CIP	NI	PM	PSC		
(5)-(+)-3-Methyl-1-pentanol																																		
.beta.-Acorenol																																		
.gamma.-Terpinene																																		
1-Butanol, 2-methyl-																																		
1-Butanol, 3-methyl-																																		
1-Penten-3-ol																																		
1-Propanol, 2-methyl-																																		
2(3H)-Furanone, dihydro-3-methyl-																																		
2,3-Hexanedione																																		
2,5-Cyclohexadiene-1,4-dione, 2,6-bis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-																																		
2,5-Hexanedione																																		
2-Cyclopenten-1-one																																		
2-Hydroxy-3-hexanone																																		
2-Hydroxy-3-pentanone																																		
2-Undecanone																																		
3-Buten-1-ol, 3-methyl-																																		
3-Cyclohexen-1-ol, 4-methyl-1-(1-methylethyl)-, (R)-																																		
3-Hexanol, 2-methyl-																																		
3-Hexen-2-one																																		
3-Pentanone																																		
3-Penten-2-one, 4-methyl-																																		
5,9-Undecadien-2-one, 6,10-dimethyl-, (Z)-																																		
5-Hepten-1-ol, 2,6-dimethyl-																																		
6-Hepten-1-ol, 2-methyl-																																		
Acetyl valeryl																																		
Aziridine, 1-ethenyl-																																		
Benzene, 4-ethyl-1,2-dimethoxy-																																		
Bicyclo[2.2.1]heptan-2-ol, 1,7,7-trimethyl-, (1S-endo)-																																		
Citronellol																																		
Cyclic octaatomic sulfur																																		
Cyclohexanol																																		
Cyclooctyl alcohol																																		
Cyclopentanone, 3-methyl-																																		
dl-Menthol																																		
Geraniol																																		
Isobutanol, TMS derivative																																		
N-Acetyl-3-pyrroline																																		
Oxalic acid, butyl propyl ester																																		
Phenol, 2-methoxy-																																		
Phenol, 4-ethyl-																																		
Phenol, 5-ethenyl-2-methoxy-																																		
Preinol																																		
Propanoic acid, anhydride																																		
Pyrrrole																																		

3.2 Pinewood nematode

There were 3 VOCs produced by PWN cultures feeding on *B. cinerea* on barley seeds in pure culture; 2-methyl-, methyl ester, 2-butanoic acid; 2-methyl 4-heptanone and 2-methyl 4-heptanol (Table 3).

Table 3 VOCs present in samples from PWN after feeding on *B. cinerea*. These compounds were not present in samples from axenic *B. cinerea* cultures.

VOC Nr.	CAS Nr.	Volatile organic compounds	Pinewood nematode feeding on <i>B. cinerea</i>
VOC1	868-57-5	2-methyl-, methyl ester, 2-butanoic acid	Mixed life stages
VOC2	626-33-5	2-methyl 4-heptanone	Mixed life stages
VOC3	21570-35-4	2-methyl 4-heptanol	Mixed life stages

3.3 Brown marmorated Stinkbug and related species

The BMSB adults produced 52 different VOCs, 41 of those were also produced by the first and second instar, and the eggs of this insect (Table 4). Tridecane was produced by adults from both the BMSB and the SGSB, a closely related species, while (Z)-alpha-bisabolene, Alpha-costol, (E,Z)-alpha-bisabolene epoxide and (Z,Z)-alpha-bisabolene epoxide were only found in the SGSB, but not in the BMSB.

Table 4. VOCs present in samples from BMSB at different stages of development. These compounds were not present in the control samples.

VOC Nr.	CAS Nr.	Volatile organic compounds	BMSB developmental stage
VOC16	65405-70-1	E-4-decenal	Adult
VOC20	2497-25-8	Z-2-decenal	Adult
VOC32	2497-23-6	E-2-decenyl acetate	Adult
VOC37	13360-61-7	1-pentadecene	Adult
VOC46	504-60-9	1,3-pentadiene	Adult
VOC47	1487-18-9	2-ethenylfuran	Adult
VOC48	6728-26-3	2-hexenal	Adult
VOC49	22122-36-7	2-methyl-2-furanone	Adult
VOC50	18829-56-6	E-2-nonenal	Adult
VOC51	93979-14-7	Methyl-E-4-decenoate	Adult
VOC52	21662-13-5	(E,Z)-2,6-Dodecadienal	Adult
VOC1	66-25-1	Hexanal	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC2	111-71-7	Heptanal	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC3	20697-55-6	E-4-oxo-2-hexenal	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC4	110-93-0	6-methyl-5-hepten-2-one	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC5	124-18-5	Decane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC6	17302-27-1	2,5-dimethyl-nonane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC7	17302-28-2	2,6-dimethyl-nonane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg

VOC8	2548-87-0	E-2-octenal	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC9	2847-72-5	4-methyl-decane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC10	98-86-2	Acetophenone	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC11	1120-21-4	Undecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC12	124-19-6	Nonanal	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC13	149-57-5	2-ethyl-hexanoic acid	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC14	513-20-2	Sabina ketone	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC15	2980-69-0	4-methyl-undecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC17	112-40-3	Dodecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC18	112-31-2	Decanal	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC19	17301-23-4	2,6-dimethyl-undecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC21	6044-71-9	6-methyl-dodecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC22	3913-81-3	E-2-decenal	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC23	17301-32-5	4,7-dimethyl-undecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC24	61141-72-8	4,6-dimethyl-dodecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC25	25152-83-4	E,Z-2,4-decadienal	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC26	629-50-5	Tridecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC27	112-44-7	Undecanal	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC28	2363-88-4	E,E-2,4-decadienal	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC29	2463-77-6	2-undecenal	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC30	1560-96-9	2-methyl-tridecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC31	629-59-4	Tetradecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC33	112-54-9	Dodecanal	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC34	25117-32-2	5-methyl-tetradecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC35	25117-24-2	4-methyl-tetradecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC36	3891-99-4	2,6,10-trimethyltridecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC38	629-62-9	Pentadecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC39	504-44-9	Croctane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC40	1560-93-6	2-methyl-pentadecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC41	544-76-3	Hexadecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC42	124-25-4	Tetradecanal	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC43	3892-00-0	2,6,10-trimethyl-pentadecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC44	593-45-3	Octadecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg
VOC45	629-92-5	Nonadecane	Adult; First Instar; Second Instar; Egg

Table 5. VOCs present in samples from SGSB

VOC Nr.	CAS Nr.	Volatile organic compounds	SGSB developmental stage
VOC1	629-50-5	Tridecane	Adult
VOC2	29837-07-8	(Z)-alpha-bisabolene	Adult
VOC3	65018-15-7	Alpha-costol	Adult
VOC4	#	(E,Z)-alpha-bisabolene epoxide	Adult
VOC5	#	(Z,Z)-alpha-bisabolene epoxide	Adults

3.4 Fall Army Worm

Two VOCs were produced by the FAW in reliable and sufficient amounts (Table 5).

Table 5 VOCs present in samples from FAW larvae at the 5th instar stage. These VOCs were not present in the control samples.

VOC Nr.	CAS Nr.	Volatile organic compounds	FAW developmental stage
VOC1	629-62-9	pentadecane	5th instar
VOC2	108-95-2	phenol	5th instar

4 CONCLUSION

Our separate studies on plant pests in pure culture have shown that the diverse pests we investigated, including 30 different oomycetes, a nematode and three insect pests, produced different, but unique VOC profiles consistently. Only one species, the oomycete *Phytophthora lili* did not produce any detectable VOC at all. These findings support our hypothesis that various plant pests produce distinct, species-specific VOC profiles and that these VOCs could serve as biological markers for plant pest detection. In the next phase of our study, we will identify and monitor VOCs from plant pests in and on their host plants to be able to determine VOC profiles that can be used to detect plant pests in their natural habitat and in realistic population density. Based on our current study we will be able to investigate if the detected VOCs produced from infested plants will originate from the host, the pest or a combination of both.

5 REFERENCES

1. Guoqing, L., Zhaojun, H., Lili, M., Xiaoran, Q., Changkun, C., & Yinchang, W. 2001. Natural oviposition-detering chemicals in female cotton bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner). *Journal of Insect Physiology*, 47(9), 951-956.
2. Liu, M., Yu, H., & Li, G. 2008. Oviposition deterrents from eggs of the cotton bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae): chemical identification and analysis by electroantennogram. *Journal of insect physiology*, 54(4), 656-662.
3. Nesbitt, B, Beever, P, Hall, D & Lester, R. 1980. (Z)-9-Hexadecenal: a minor component of the female sex pheromone of *Heliiothis armigera* (Hübner) (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae). *Entomologia experimentalis et Applicata* 27: 306–08.
4. Piccardi, P, Capizzi, A, Cassani, G, Spinelli, P, Arsur, E, et al. 1977. A sex pheromone component of the Old World bollworm *Heliiothis armigera*. *Journal of Insect Physiology* 23: 1443–45.
5. Xu, H., Li, G., Liu, M., & Xing, G. 2006. Oviposition deterrents in larval frass of the cotton boll worm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae): Chemical identification and electroantennography analysis. *Journal of Insect Physiology*, 52(3), 320-326.
6. Zhang, JP, Salcedo, C, Fang, YL, Zhang, RJ & Zhang, ZN. 2012. An overlooked component: (Z)-9-tetradecenal as a sex pheromone in *Helicoverpa armigera*. *Journal of Insect Physiology* 58: 1209–16.

